

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES FOR CFRP/DAMPING-MATERIAL LAMINATES

J. FUJIMOTO and T. TAMURA

Resources & Environment Protection Research Laboratories, NEC Corp.
Kawasaki 213, JAPAN

K. TODOME

Space Development Division, NEC Corp., Yokohama 227, JAPAN

T. TANIMOTO

Department of Materials Science and Ceramic Technology,
Shonan Institute of Technology, Fujisawa 251, JAPAN

Y. SUZUKI and K. KAUCHI

Advanced Materials & Products Laboratories,
Mitsui Petrochemical Ind., Ltd., Kimitu 299-02, JAPAN

ABSTRACT

New materials, that possess high damping capability and have high strength property, have been studied in carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP). These materials, used in spacecraft, are referred to in this paper as CFRP/damping-material laminates. CFRP/damping-material laminates investigated here are composed of the unidirectional carbon/epoxy prepreg sheet and polyethylene based damping material sheet used as an interleaf. Cantilever beam tests revealed the high damping properties of these laminates. Loss factor values for these composites are from 5 through 50 times as large as that for conventional CFRP. These values could be predicted by using the analysis constrained layer damping treatment except for two specimens. Also, the interleaving effect on tensile strength are discussed here. Tensile test results for quasi-isotropic laminates based composites indicated that the damping material interleaf is effective for suppressing delamination and multiple splitting in the 0° angle layer. A 3 through 8% ultimate load increase was caused by this suppression effect.

KEYWORDS: Composites; Polymer; Fiber/Graphite; Vibration; Damping

1. INTRODUCTION

Because a significant number of spacecraft failures and anomalies are related to severe vibration during launch and ground tests, vibration reduction offers not only an increase in satellite reliability but also a decrease in development and operating costs.

Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) have been widely used for spacecraft structures, due to their high-stiffness and low-density properties. However, these composite materials are unsuitable for obtaining low-vibration structures. When using these materials, structures were usually fabricated using adhesively-bonded joints, which replaced bolts and rivets. This seriously reduces the damping caused by friction at joints (structural damping) and so makes material damping far more important in comparison with conventional structures. CFRP has low vibration damping property (loss factor $\eta = 0.001-0.01$), similar to conventional structural materials. It is thus very important to improve the vibration damping property for fiber reinforced composites, especially in spacecraft applications.

New kinds of carbon fiber reinforced plastics have been developed in the present work to improve vibration damping capability. These materials were fabricated by sandwiching the damping material between layer interfaces in CFRP. [1,2] This paper presents vibration damping properties and tensile strength for CFRP/damping material laminates.

2. MATERIALS AND METHOD

Unidirectional prepreg sheets (T800/#2500, TORAY Industries, Inc.) and polyethylene based damping materials were used throughout this study. Figure 1 gives viscoelastic properties for the damping material sheets. These properties were measured at 96 cps vibration. The loss tangent $\tan\delta$ maximum was about 0.9 at room temperature. The damping material sheets were about 70 μ m thick and were sandwiched between thermo-adhesive surface layers. Figure 2 gives the stacking sequence for the various laminates formed using a vacuum bagging/autoclave curing technique. Type I to Type VIII are $[0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ]_s$ quasi-isotropic laminates. Type I was a conventional CFRP. Type II through Type VIII were CFRP/damping-material laminates. Type IX and Type X are $[+45^\circ_2/-45^\circ_2]_s$ angle-ply laminates, and Type XI and Type XII are $[0^\circ_2/90^\circ_2]_s$ cross-ply laminates.

A cantilever beam test was conducted for obtaining dynamic mechanical properties for these composite laminates.[1] Loss factor η was determined by the decay curve for vibration. The flexural modulus values for individual composites were calculated using the natural vibration frequencies for the beams. Test beam dimensions were 250mm x 30mm. Composites thicknesses were from 1.2 to 1.8mm. Furthermore, dynamic mechanical properties under tensile cyclic deformation were measured by a viscoelastic spectrometer at 100cps. Test beam dimensions used were 30mm x 3mm. Tensile strength was evaluated with an Instron type testing machine. Test specimens dimensions are 250mm x 25mm. Ten specimens were tested for Type I to Type VIII

laminates. Three specimens each were tested for Type IX through Type X II laminates.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3-1. Mechanical Dynamic Properties Figures 3 and 4 illustrate the loss factor with temperature change for Type I and Type III specimens. The conventional CFRP (Type I) shows lower loss factor values. These values were nearly 0.003, and remain approximately constant with temperature and frequency. On the contrary, the Type III specimen indicates larger temperature and frequency dependencies. With increases in temperature and mode number, the loss factor value increases. These dependencies are closely related to viscoelastic properties of the damping material, as shown Fig 1. The maximum loss factor value for the Type III specimen is about 0.3, which is about 100 times as large as that for the conventional CFRP Type I specimens. Figure 5 indicates loss factor and flexural modulus for Type I through Type X II specimens in the third mode vibration at 30°C. It is seen, in this figure, that loss factor values for CFRP/damping material laminates are 5 through 50 times as large as those for conventional materials, Type I, Type IX, and Type X I specimens. Furthermore, these properties depend strongly on both the number of damping sheets and their incorporated positions. On the contrary, the flexural modulus for CFRP/damping material laminates shows slightly lower values than those obtained with conventional materials. The degree of change in flexural modulus, however, is extremely small, in comparison with that for the loss factor. These results suggest that CFRP/damping-material laminates offer great promise for obtaining low-vibration structure.

The analysis, developed by Ross, Ungar, and Kerwin (referred to hereafter as the RKU analysis), was used to predict damping properties for CFRP/damping material laminates.[3] Two basic analytical models used here are symmetric constrained layer and sandwich beam configurations. Figure 6 shows analytic models and their complex flexural rigidity. Loss factor η for the composite plate was determined by the ratio of real and imaginary components in the flexural rigidity. Loss factor values for Type IV, Type V, Type VI, Type X, and Type X II specimens were calculated from the symmetric constrained layer model, as shown in Fig 6 (a). Loss factor values for Type II specimen were calculated from the sandwich beam model, as shown in Fig 6 (b). The remaining specimens, Type III, Type VII, Type VIII, and Type X III specimens, have three damping sheets or more. In these cases, the above models cannot be used themselves for predicting the damping performance. Therefore, the authors attempted to use an approximation, where most of the shear deformation occurs in the inner damping layers, closest to the neutral plan of the composite beam. This approximation has made it possible to simplify the configurations for Type III, Type VII, and Type X III to the sandwich beam model, as well as to simplify the configurations for Type VIII to the symmetric constrained layer model. Figures 7 and 8 illustrate the comparison between predicted and measured loss factor values for CFRP/damping material laminates. Figure 7 shows the obtained results for the Type X III specimen. It

can be seen, in the figure, that agreement between predicted and measured values is very good. Results for the Type X specimen are shown in Fig. 8. As $\pm 45^\circ$ angle-ply laminated the Type IX specimen have relatively large loss factor values (0.003-0.009). Predicted values for the Type X specimen was obtained by using these values as the loss factor for stiff layers 1 and 3 (see Fig. 6). It is seen that predicted values differ greatly from measured values, in spite of the above consideration. Plots, showing measured loss factor values versus predicted loss factor values for all CFRP/damping material laminates, are shown in Fig. 9. Good agreement was obtained, except for the results for Type III and Type X specimens. This indicates that the RKU analysis is applicable for predicting damping properties for CFRP/damping material laminates. On the other hand, measured values for Type III and Type X specimens are about three times greater than predicted values. Figure 10 indicates the results for the damping capability under flexural and tensile deformation in $\pm 45^\circ$ angle-ply laminated Type IX and Type X specimens. It was found that the Type X CFRP/damping material laminates has large loss factor values under tensile deformation, in addition to flexural deformation. Similar properties were observed in the Type III specimen. The RKU analysis was basically directed to the materials which possess isotropic properties. In such a meaning, loss factor values for the Type X specimen under tensile deformation are considered to have values closer to those for the Type IX specimen, in contrast with the results indicated in Fig. 10. These results suggest that large loss factor values under tensile deformation, as well as the large discrepancy between predicted and measured values, as shown in Fig. 9, are probably caused by anisotropic properties in these laminates.

3-2. Tensile Strength Experimental and computation tensile results are listed in Table 1. These values were obtained from 25mm wide specimens. Some of the quasi-isotropic laminates based composite materials show larger ultimate load (UL) values, in comparison with the conventional Type I specimen. Type II, Type IV, Type VI and Type VIII specimens, whose UL values are 26,4kN, 26.1kN, 26,4kN and 26.1kN, have 3 and 5% larger UL value, in comparison with the Type I value, 25.2kN. The largest UL value was obtained in the Type VII specimen. This UL value was 27,1kN (8% increase). The reason for the improvement achieved in these specimens is considered to be due to the suppressing the multiple splitting in 0° angle layer and delamination between 45° and 90° angle layers, which are a predominant fracture mode in the conventional Type I specimen.[1] The coefficient of variation (Cv) values, which are related to tensile strength reliability, are also listed in Table 1. Cv values for CFRP/damping-material laminates, except for the Type III specimen, are lower than the value for the Type I specimen. This result suggests that CFRP/damping-material laminates have highly reliable tensile strength. On the other hand, angle-ply and cross-ply based CFRP/damping-material laminates, which are Type X and Type X II specimens, show lower UL values, in comparison with values for conventional Type IX and Type X I specimens. In particular, the decrement degree in Type X specimen, that have large loss factor values under tensile cyclic deformation, is extremely large. Notice that tensile strength and damping capability under tensile deformation are conflicting properties. Similar results were obtained in the Type III specimen.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This investigation on CFRP/damping-material laminates led to the following conclusions:

1. CFRP/damping-material laminates have 5 through 50 times larger loss factor values at 30°C, in comparison with conventional CFRP values. These properties depend on both the number of damping sheets and their incorporated positions. On the contrary, the flexural modulus for these laminates shows slightly lower values than the values obtained with conventional materials.
2. Loss factor values for CFRP/damping-material laminates could be predicted, except for Type III and Type X specimens, using equations for constrained layer damping treatments developed by Ross, Ungar and Kerwin. These two specimens show large loss factor values, even under tensile cyclic deformation.
3. The damping-material interleaf has been shown to increase the ultimate load and to improve the tensile strength reliability in quasi-isotropic laminates, except for Type III specimen.
4. The ultimate load decrements for Type III and Type X specimens, that have large loss factor values under tensile cyclic deformation, are extremely large.

5. REFERENCES

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Table1 Tensile strength for various types of laminates.

Specimen	Ultimate Load U_L (kN)	Coefficient of Variation C_v (%)
Type I	25.2	5.69
Type II	26.4	3.07
Type III	22.9	6.51
Type IV	26.1	4.33
Type V	25.1	2.84
Type VI	26.4	4.90
Type VII	27.1	1.36
Type VIII	26.1	1.77
Type IX	4.1	—
Type X	2.2	—
Type X I	39.6	—
Type X II	39.0	—

Fig.1 Viscoelastic properties for damping material sheet.

Fig.2 Stacking sequence for CFRP/damping-material laminates.

Fig.3 Loss factor versus temperature for Type I specimen.

Fig.4 Loss factor versus temperature for Type III specimen.

Fig.5 Loss factor and flexural modulus for laminates in 3rd. vibration mode.
 (a)Loss factor (b)Flexural modulus

(a) Symmetric constrained layer

$$B^* = \frac{E_1^* H_1^3}{12} + \frac{E_3^* H_3^3}{6} + 2E_3^* H_3 H_{31}^2 \frac{g^*}{1+g^*}$$

(b) Sandwich beam

$$B^* = \frac{E_1^* H_1^3}{6} + E_3^* H_3^3 H_{31}^2 \frac{g^*}{1+2g^*} \quad (E_1 = E_3, H_1 = H_3)$$

where

$$H_{31} = \frac{E_1 + H_3}{2} + H_2, \quad g^* = \frac{G_2^* L^2}{E_3 H_3 H_2 \xi_n^2}$$

- E_1^* ; complex Young's modulus , G_2^* ; complex shear modulus of damping layer
- L ; beam length , ξ_n ; nth eigenvalue , H_i ; beam element thickness
- B^* ; complex flexural rigidity

Fig.6 Analytical models for damping properties.

Fig.7 Predicted and measured loss factor versus temperature for Type X III specimen.

Fig.8 Predicted and measured loss factor versus temperature for Type X specimen.

Fig.9 Relation between predicted and measured values.
 (a) Predicted values, using symmetric constrained layer model
 (b) Predicted values, using sandwich beam model

Fig.10 Loss factor values under tensile and flexural deformations for Type IX and Type X specimens.